

COVID^X

We are almost there! #BackToAHealthyFutureEvent

Get to know more about the speakers, the companies exhibiting, the roundtables and the matchmaking sessions. Register for the event!

[Register now](#)

Get inspired by the Inspirational talks at #BackToAHealthyFuture

Learn more about the happy and healthy workplaces at the #BacktoAHealthyFutureEvent.

[Learn more](#)

Watch these webinars!

Learn more about customer segmentation in healthcare, value proposition design, journey mapping or marketing and growth funnels with the OC2 webinars!

[Learn more](#)

ODIN Open Call
420,000€ available for AI
and Big Data solutions
Join us!

➔ **#ODINopencall**

The ODIN Open Call is open until October 27th at 17:00 CET

ODIN's Open Call→Are you an startup, SME, midcap, industry, research centre or technology organization? Get involved in the #ODINopencall, they are looking for entities leading AI, BigData, DataAnalytics in healthcare to join them!

[Open Call](#)

PHIRI's workshop

“Towards Foresight informed policy making” will take place between 9.00-12.00 CEST on the 19th of September. Register now!

EU's CO-VERSATILE Project round-up virtual event

To find out more about the event, log on [here](#).

COVID-X

www.covid-x.eu / info@covid-x.eu

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